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Molecular and Histopathological Studies on Currently Circulating RHDV in Rabbit Farms in Egypt

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Abstract

The current study aimed to identify rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus (RHDV) causing high mortality in rabbit farms from May 2018 to December 2020 as well as its genetic variation and histopathological picture in natural outbreaks. A total of 12 rabbit flocks from different localities of Alexandria governorate were investigated for RHDV depending on the mortalities, clinical signs, post mortem lesions, HA (hemagglutination) and conventional PCR. Partial sequencing for selected one isolate was applied, then nucleotide sequences were accessed on GenBank. The positive findings indicated that 10 out of 12 rabbit flocks were positive for RHDV. On the basis of phylogenetic tree, the selected one isolate was clustered with the newly emerged RHDV2 circulating in Egypt and accessed in GeneBank as follow MW679028RHDV Maryout. It had a similarity of 99.8% with Abotaleb strain, 99.2% with Alex B 18 strain and Alex 19 strain as well as 93.1-93.3% with Menofia, Kaliobia, Sharkia, Dakahlia, and Bahira strains. It was concluded that the isolate named MW679028 RHDV Maryout belonged to RHDV2 and not related to the classic vaccinal strain in Egypt causing high mortalities in both vaccinated and non-vaccinated rabbit flocks. So that a new vaccine of RHDV2 should be applied in rabbit farms with the old classic vaccine at the same time.

Keywords: Rabbits, RHDV, RT-PCR, Sequence, Viruses

Introduction

Rabbit hemorrhagic disease (RHD) is a serious and extremely contagious viral disease affecting all ages of wild and domestic rabbits accompanied by high mortality of approximately 90% (Abrantes et al., 2012).

Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus (RHDV) is a major pathogen for rabbits all over the world (Mcintosh et al., 2007) belongs to family Caliciviridae, genus lagovirus (Thiel and König 1999). There are many strains of RHDV, and three major viral subtypes: RHDV ("classical RHDV"), the antigenic variant RHDVa, and the recently emerged virus RHDV2 (also called RHDVb). Classical RHDV and RHDVa comprise one serotype, while RHDV2 belongs to a different serotype (Le Gall-Reculé, 2013).

The phylogenetic analyses were based mainly on the alignment of gene sequences (full or fragmentary) coding for the VP60 structural protein and vp30 non-structural one (Fitzner et al., 2012).

Studies from Australia, China, Czech Republic, France, Italy, Ireland, Korea, Mexico, New Zealand, Poland, Spain and the USA concerning the genetic variation over 100 RHDV strains have shown that it is 14% (Milton et al., 1992; Boga et al., 1994; Gould et al., 1997; Moss et al., 2002; Le Gall Recule et al., 2003; Matiz et al., 2006; Chrobocińska, 2007; Tian et al., 2007; Yang et al., 2008; HukowskaSzematowicz et al., 2009; Muller et al., 2009; Oem et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2012).

Another recent estimation done by Le Gall-Recule et al., (2011), who investigated 125 RHDV strains, showed that genetic variation amounting to 14.3%.

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RHDV was classified in accordance to the time and site of their isolation, the earlier investigation determined three genogroups (G1-G3), while the more recent study (Le Gall-Recule et al., 2003), in which five RHDVa strains were also included, distinguished six genogroups (G1-G6).

Even more groups were identified by researchers working on British RHDV strains and samples collected between 1950 and 1980 (Moss et al., 2002). That phylogenetic analysis, also based on an alignment of VP60 gene fragment, classified the investigated strains and samples into eight genogroups.

In Egypt, the first recorded outbreak was at 1991 in Sharkia governorate (Ghanem and Ismail 1992) then reported in many other governorates with severe losses 90% and appeared in winter 1993 in upper Egypt for the first time in Minea, Assuit, and Sohag governorates with mortality rate ranges from 26 up to 100% in adult rabbits (El-Zanaty, 1994).

About 25 outbreaks of RHD was investigated in many Egyptian governorates as Giza, Cairo, Marsa matrouh, Kalubia, Kafr-El -Sheikh and Gharbia since 1994 until 1996 (Ibrahim et al., 1999).

Recently during the last few years, there were high dramatic mortalities up to 100% in either vaccinated or non-vaccinated rabbit farms. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the causative agent and its genetic relationship in addition to histopathological alterations in naturally affected rabbit farms.

Materials and methods

Samples collection and processing

Liver tissues of 12 different rabbit flocks (5 rabbits per each flock) suffering from respiratory symptoms, a severe dyspnea, lethargy, off food, diarrhea, and high mortalities were collected between May 2018 and December 2020. The area of investigation included Alexandria desert road in Egypt (Table 1). Those tissue samples were grounded with repeated freezing and thawing for three times in phosphate buffer saline of a pH of 7.0 to 7.4 containing gentamycin (50 µg/mL) and Mycostatin (1,000 units/mL) to make 10% suspension then centrifuged at 3000 rpm/10 min. Tissue supernatant was collected and stored at - 80°C until being tested for reisolation, HA (haemagglutination) and conventional PCR for the investigation of rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus (RHDV).

Table 1: History of affected rabbit flocks with RHDV

Sample No (farm)	Date	Total No of Rabbits	Breed/age	Area (Alexandria)	Vaccination	Mortality%
1	20/5/2018 spring	200	Multiple (California, New Zealand, Flander, Rex) /5 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Amria 1 st outbreak	Ukraine RHDV	16%
2	13/9/2018 autumn	160	Multiple/6 wks - \geq 4 ms	Borg El-Arab	Non vaccinated	60%
3	20/9/2018 autumn	140	Multiple/6 wks - \geq 4 ms	North coast kilo 46	Egyptian RHDV	42%
4	23/9/2018 autumn	180	Multiple/4 wks - \geq 4 ms	North coast kilo 38	Spain RHDV	35%
5	24/9/2018 autumn	230	Multiple/4 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Amria	Spain RHDV	63%
6	27/9/2018 autumn	100	Multiple/5 wks - \geq 4 ms	Kilo 40 Alex- Cairo desert road	Egyptian RHDV	70%
7	30/9/2018 autumn	160	Multiple/5 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Amria 2 nd outbreak	Ukraine RHDV	78%
8	2/12/2018 winter	65	Multiple/5 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Nahda	Spain RHDV	58%
9	6/2/2019 winter	120	Multiple/6 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Hawaria	Egyptian RHDV	53%
10	22/6/2019 summer	50	Multiple/5 wks - \geq 4 ms	Abees	Spain RHDV	61%
11	21/7/2019	125	Multiple/6 wks - \geq 4 ms	El-Salam	Non vaccinated	56%

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	summer					
12	26/12/2020 winter	150	Multiple/6 wks - ≥ 4 ms	Maryout	Non vaccinated	92%

Wks: weeks

ms: months

Positive control virus

Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus (RHDV) was kindly supplied by viral strains bank department in central laboratory for evaluation of veterinary biologics which used as positive control in both preparation of RHDV-HA antigen and RT-PCR technique.

sample inoculation and purification

10 susceptible 2-3 months old rabbits weighed 1.5 to 2.5 kg were tested negative for anti RHDV antibodies then inoculated intramuscularly with 1 ml of the 10% liver homogenate. Keeping two rabbits as negative control and observed for one week for the appearance of clinical manifestation and re-isolation of the virus from livers of inoculated animals (Ferreira et al 2004) all test procedure occurred under the Ethics and Animal Experiments Committee regulations.

Haemagglutination test (HA)

Collection of type (O) human blood on 4% sodium citrate, an equal volume of PBS was added to the blood with gentle mixing and centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 5 minutes then discard the supernatant and repeat this step two to three times to wash the red blood cells from any debris, resuspend the sedimented RBCs in PBS to make 1% suspension. The liver homogenates were subjected to rapid haemagglutination (RHA) test then micro plate HA test performed in a V-shaped bottom micro titer plates, two-fold serial dilution of the extracted liver fluid in PBS PH 7.2 adding an equal amount of 1% washed human RBCs, incubate at 4°C finally recording the haemagglutination titer was the highest dilution giving complete agglutination of erythrocytes (OIE 2018).

RNA extraction.

RNA extraction from samples was performed using the QIAamp viral RNA Mini kit (Qiagen, Germany, GmbH). Briefly, 140 µl of the sample suspension was incubated with 560 µl of AVL lysis buffer and 5.6 µl of carrier RNA at room temperature for 10 min. After incubation, 560 µl of 100% ethanol was added to the lysate. The sample washed and centrifuged following the manufacturer's recommendations. Nucleic acid was eluted with 60 µl of elution buffer provided in the kit.

Oligonucleotide Primers.

supplied from (Metabion Germany) are listed in table (2).

Table 2: Primers sequences, target genes, amplicon sizes

Target gene	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Length of amplified product (bp)	Reference
VP60	P33: CCACCACCAACACTTCAGGT	538 bp	Fahmy <i>et al.</i> , 2010
	P34: CAGGTTGAACACGAGTGTGC		

Conventional polymerase chain reaction

PCR amplification

Primers were utilized in a 25- µl reaction containing 12.5 µl of Quantitect probe rt-PCR buffer (QIAGEN, GmbH), 1 µl of each primer of 20 pmol concentration, 0.25 µl of rt-enzyme 4.25 µl of water, and 6 µl of template. The reaction was performed in a Biometra thermal cycler. Reverse transcription was applied at 50 °C for 30 min, a primary denaturation step was done at 95 °C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles

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of 94°C for 30 sec., 56°C for 40 sec. and 72°C for 45 sec. min. A final extension step was done at 72°C for 10 min.

Analysis of the PCR Product

The products of PCR were separated by electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose gel (Appllichem, Germany, GmbH) in 1x TBE buffer at room temperature using gradients of 5V/cm. For gel analysis, 15 µl of the products was loaded in each gel slot. A generuler 100 bp DNA ladder (Fermentas, Germany) was used to determine the fragment sizes. The gel was photographed by a gel documentation system (Alpha Innotech, Biometra) and the data was analyzed through computer software.

Sequencing, phylogenetic analysis and GenBank accession

One RHDV isolate was selected for Sequencing, phylogenetic analysis and GenBank accession depending on its recent incidence, high percent of mortality with severity of signs and PM (Post Mortem) lesions. PCR products were purified using QIAquick PCR Product extraction kit. (Qiagen, Valencia). Bigdye Terminator V3.1 cycle sequencing kit (Perkin-Elmer) was used for the sequence reaction and then it was purified using Centrisep spin column. DNA sequences were obtained by Applied Biosystems3130 genetic analyzer (HITACHI, Japan), a BLAST® analysis (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) (Altschul *et al.*, 1990) was initially performed to establish sequence identity to GenBank accession. The phylogenetic tree was created by the MegAlign module of LasergeneDNASTar version 12.1 (Thompson *et al.*, 1994) and Phylogenetic analyses was done using maximum likelihood, neighbour joining and maximum parsimony in MEGA6 (Tamura *et al.*, 2013).

Histopathological examination

Autopsy samples were taken from the liver, kidney, lung and heart of rabbits from different farms and fixed in 10% formalin saline for twenty-four hours. Washing was done in tap water the serial dilutions of alcohol (methyl, ethyl and absolute ethyl) were used for dehydration. Specimens were cleared in xylene and embedded in paraffin at 56 degrees in hot air oven for twenty-four hours. Paraffin bees wax tissue blocks were prepared for sectioning at 4 microns' thickness by slide microtome. The obtained tissue sections were collected on glass slides, de-paraffinized, stained by hematoxylin & eosin stain then examined through the light electric microscope (Banchroft *et al.*, 1996).

Ethical approval

The present study was affirmed by the Ethics Committee of both Animal Health Division, Desert Research Center and Central Laboratory for Evaluation of Veterinary Biologics, Egypt.

Results and discussion

According to FAO 2019, Egypt is one of the five major producers of rabbit meat, where Italy was the first largest producer of rabbit meat in the world, followed by China, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Spain, and Egypt.

rabbits play an important role in the production of both meat and fur, so that the prevention and control of its diseases should be continuously applied (Isomursu *et al.*, 2018).

RHD is one of the common major disease in rabbits called rabbit plaque causing severe economic losses in rabbit industry (Hukowska-Szematowicz *et al.*, 2012).

Natural outbreaks

On overview from table (1), our findings stated that rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus (RHDV) occurred in different seasons of the year (more common in autumn season) and affected multiple rabbit breeds at different ages begin with 4 weeks old. Also findings revealed that RHDV affected both non-

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vaccinated and vaccinated rabbit flocks with different vaccine (Egyptian, Ukraine, and Spain RHDV vaccine) with mortality ranged from 16-92%. These results coincide with that of Ahmed and Azhar (2020) who reported rabbits <28 days old were found to be susceptible to RHDV where the samples were collected from rabbits at different ages and during different seasons (most common in summer) and suggested both classical RHDV and RHDV2 might have comparatively equal virulence during natural outbreaks. El-Zanaty (1994) noted that RHDV was identified in rabbits during the spring of 1991 in Sharkia Province associated with 90% losses in addition to mortality ranged 26.7 - 100% among 14-16 week-old rabbits during winter and spring of 1993 in upper Egypt (Minya, Assiut, and Sohag Provinces). Le Gall-Recule et al., (2013) reported the disease associated with RHDV2 had a similar form of classical RHDV, although the mortality rates might be more variable with tendency to be lower. Ewees, (2007) proved that RHDV1 infected multiple breeds mainly adult age (more than 5 months) but rabbits (1-3months old) were less affected. Ruvoen-clouet et al., (2000) said that adult rabbits were more susceptible than young for infection by classic RHDV due to presence of ABH antigen in the epithelial of upper respiratory tract and digestive tract of adult in contrast young age rabbit. Also, El-Bagoury et al., (2014) found the collected samples from vaccinated or non-vaccinated rabbits were equal for RHDV infection.

Clinical signs and Post Mortem lesions (PM)

Affected rabbits in all farms exhibited sudden death with or without nostril bleeding specially in adult juvenile rabbits while in old ages found lethargy, off food, difficult breathing and diarrhea.

Dead rabbits showed distended urinary bladder with dark turbid urine, general congestion and hemorrhage in lungs, livers and kidneys.

Experimental viral inoculation and identification

The rabbits inoculated with 1 ml of 10% liver extract of the suspected liver samples showed various responses as sudden death with or without nostril bleeding, off food, difficult breathing and diarrhea while postmortem lesions recorded general congestion and hemorrhage in lungs, livers and kidneys with urinary bladder distension. The control negative rabbits didn't show any deaths or clinical manifestation. The outstanding results of Clinical signs and PM lesions either in nature or experiment supported by Beata et al 2006 who reported death of four non-immunized and survival of seven vaccinated rabbits at 48–72 h post infection showing the typical clinical signs of rabbit hemorrhagic disease (RHD), also Yang et al 2015 stated that the immunized rabbits showed 100% survival rates without any clinical signs of RHD, furthermore, there were no surviving rabbits in the control group by 14 days. Naglaa and Gamelat 2018 observed few rabbits showing sudden deaths with frothy bloody exudate from nostrils or vagina or Hematuria, whereas other rabbits revealed dullness, depression, convulsion, fever with cyanosis of lips and nostrils, dyspnea accompanied by abdominal respiration. While on PM observed an opisonous position of dead rabbits with severe congestion and frothy exudate in whole trachea as well as congested, edematous and hemorrhagic lungs. The liver appeared pale, yellowish brown in color with focal, lobular necrosis with scattered hemorrhage of variable sizes. Urinary bladder appeared full-filled with engorged blood vessels. Metwally and Madbouly (2005); Em-bury-Hyatt et al., (2012) recorded rabbit inoculation was the only way of isolation, propagation and titration of RHDV since its in-vitro replication system is unachieved till now.

Haemagglutination test (HA)

HA test showed that 10 out of 12 rabbit flocks were positive with haemagglutinating titers ranged from 10 to 17 log 2 as shown in (table 3), where 6 log 2 considered negative result in rabbit flock number 6 and 11.

Table 3: Haemagglutination titers of affected rabbit flocks (log 2)

Rabbit flock No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Titer	10	11	17	13	12	6	10	13	12	10	6	13

Results of conventional polymerase chain reaction

The PCR products of VP60 gene revealed positive results for RHDV at the specific amplification of 538 bp fragments for all investigated samples except that of rabbit flock number 6 and 11 (Figure 1). The results of the RT-PCR confirmed the results of the HA test as all samples gave positive results in haemagglutination test were positive when RT-PCR was applied. Our findings are consistent with those reported earlier by Le Gall-Reculé et al., (2017) regarding the efficacy of VP60 as a target for PCR assays and as a general screening tool for rabbit and hare caliciviruses. The VP60 gene was used to develop universal Lagovirus PCR primers that span a highly conserved region within RHDV (Strive et al., 2009). Ahmed and Azhar (2020) identified 16 cases that were positive for RHDV using PCR, and these 16 cases were hemagglutinin-positive, with titers ranging from 29 to 216. Le Gall-Recule et al., (2013) confirmed the use of HA as a routine diagnostic tool for the detection of RHDV2 in infected samples. On the contrary, Abd El-Moaty et al., 2014 mentioned that haemagglutination test was no longer a reliable test in diagnosis of RHDV, Guittre et al., 1995 reported the application of RT-PCR assay was more sensitive, ideal rapid and low cost tool for diagnosis of RHDV as well as Rawhia, et al., (2020) found one sample was RHDV positive by RT-PCR although it was HA negative when tested by HA test.

Sequencing, phylogenetic analysis and GenBank accession

The phylogenetic tree of VP60 gene showed that The selected RHDV isolate, Maryout 2020 was accessed in GeneBank as follow MW679028 RHDV Maryout (Table 4) and was compared with Egyptian classic RHDV, variant RHDVa, newly emerged RHDV2 and vaccinal RHDV Giza 2006. The findings indicated that the selected isolate was genetically related to the newly emerged RHDV2 and clustered in the same branch of the isolated Egyptian RHD viruses during 2018-2019 including Abotaleb strain with 83 bootstrap value and an amino acid sequence identity of 99.8%, Alex B 18 and Alex 19 strains with 88 bootstrap value and an amino acid sequence identity of 99.2 % as well as Menofia, Kaliobia, Sharkia, Dakahlia, and Bahira strains with 89 bootstrap value and an amino acid sequence identity of 93.1-93.3% (Figure 2; 3). The genetic variation of the selected RHDV isolate was 0-3.4%, 21-22.2%, 19.8-20.6% and 21.4% when compared with RHDV2, RHDVa, classic RHDV and vaccinal strain Giza 2006 respectively (Figure 3). Le Gall-Reculé et al., (2011) and Peacock et al., (2017) stated that a virus, had a capsid protein sequence identity of about 80% with RHDV2 and was able to cause RHD in vaccinated and young rabbits (15– 25 days old). Rawhia, et al., (2020) found the nucleotide divergence, 0.9-4.5% within classical group, 1.3-7.3% within RHDV2 isolates, 14.4-20.6% between two groups, and 11.2-21.2% when compared the new isolates RHDV2 with vaccine strain (RHDV-Giza 2006). In this study the highest genetic variation between the newly emerged RHDV2 and the commonly used RHDV- Giza 2006 considered the main reason leading to an equal affection of both vaccinated and non-vaccinated rabbit flocks, Lopes et al., (2015) recorded the vaccine mismatch was the etiology of continuous distribution, appearance, and gradual replacement of RHDV2. Rawhia, et al., (2020) detected both classical RHDV and newly emergent RHDV2 (GenBank accessions numbers MN295014-MN295029) circulating in different regions of Egypt with nucleotide identities of 78.4-100%. On the contrary, Naglaa and Gamelat 2018 mentioned the current RHDV outbreaks in Egypt was related to inadequate vaccine application and not vaccine mismatch.

Table 4: GenBank accession of selected recent RHDV isolate

Region	Rabbit flock NO.	Date of isolation	Accession NO.	Genotype
Maryout, Alexandria	12	26/12/2020	MW679028	RHDV2

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Figure 1: Electrophoretic pattern of RHDV-VP60 gene PCR product on 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis. **Lane (L):** 100 bp ladder. **Lane (P):** positive control. **Lane (N):** negative control. **Lane 1-5; 7-10; 12:** Positive rabbit flocks. **Lane 6; 11:** Negative rabbit flocks.

Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree showing the genetic relationships between circulating RHDV and the selected isolate for the VP60 gene (indicated by red dots).

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	Percent Identity																											
Divergence	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
1	90.7	98.8	98.6	98.8	98.4	100.0	98.2	98.4	79.2	95.8	94.3	89.1	90.3	89.7	90.5	79.0	79.2	80.2	79.8	80.2	80.0	79.4	79.4	79.2	79.2	79.6	80.2	1
2	10.1	90.7	90.5	89.5	89.3	90.7	90.1	89.3	79.2	92.1	91.1	88.9	88.7	90.3	98.8	79.0	79.2	78.6	78.2	78.6	78.4	77.8	77.8	78.0	78.0	78.0	78.6	2
3	12	10.1	99.8	97.6	97.4	98.8	97.4	97.4	79.8	94.9	93.9	88.7	89.9	88.9	90.5	79.6	79.8	80.0	79.6	80.0	79.8	79.2	79.2	79.4	79.4	79.4	80.0	3
4	14	10.4	0.2	97.4	97.2	98.6	97.2	97.2	80.0	94.7	93.7	88.5	89.7	88.7	90.3	79.8	80.0	80.2	79.8	80.2	80.0	79.4	79.4	79.6	79.6	79.6	80.2	4
5	12	11.6	2.5	2.7	97.2	98.8	97.0	97.2	78.8	94.5	93.1	88.1	89.3	88.7	89.3	78.6	78.8	80.2	79.8	80.2	80.0	79.4	79.4	79.2	79.2	79.6	80.2	5
6	1.6	11.9	2.7	2.9	2.9	98.4	97.2	100.0	78.6	94.3	93.3	88.1	89.3	88.5	89.3	78.4	78.6	79.4	79.0	79.4	79.2	79.0	78.6	78.6	78.6	78.8	79.4	6
7	0.0	10.1	1.2	1.4	1.2	1.6	98.2	98.4	79.2	95.8	94.3	89.1	90.3	89.7	90.5	79.0	79.2	80.2	79.8	80.2	80.0	79.4	79.4	79.2	79.2	79.6	80.2	7
8	1.9	10.9	2.7	2.9	3.1	2.9	1.9	97.2	78.8	94.7	93.7	88.7	89.1	88.5	89.9	78.6	78.6	79.4	79.0	79.8	79.2	78.6	78.6	78.8	78.8	78.8	79.4	8
9	1.6	11.9	2.7	2.9	2.9	0.0	1.6	2.9	78.6	94.3	93.3	88.1	89.3	88.5	89.3	78.4	78.6	79.4	79.0	79.4	79.2	79.0	78.6	78.6	78.6	78.8	79.4	9
10	25.2	25.3	24.3	24.0	25.9	26.1	25.2	25.9	26.1	79.8	80.8	79.4	78.6	79.0	79.2	99.4	99.2	93.5	93.1	93.5	93.3	94.1	94.1	94.1	94.1	96.0	93.5	10
11	4.4	8.5	5.3	5.5	5.7	6.0	4.4	5.5	6.0	24.2	79.8	80.8	80.3	92.3	90.9	91.9	79.6	79.8	79.4	79.0	79.8	79.2	79.0	79.0	79.2	79.4	79.4	11
12	6.0	9.7	6.4	6.7	7.3	7.1	6.0	6.7	7.1	22.8	2.3	89.3	91.5	90.1	90.9	80.6	80.8	80.2	79.8	80.6	80.0	79.8	79.8	79.8	79.8	80.4	80.2	12
13	12.0	12.3	12.5	12.8	13.3	13.0	12.5	13.3	14.8	10.5	11.8	93.1	96.0	88.7	79.2	79.4	77.4	77.4	77.6	77.0	77.0	77.0	77.0	77.0	77.6	77.8	13	
14	10.6	12.6	11.0	11.3	11.8	11.0	10.6	12.0	11.8	26.1	8.2	9.1	7.3	93.1	88.5	78.8	79.0	79.0	78.6	78.6	78.8	78.2	78.2	78.4	78.4	78.8	79.0	14
15	11.3	10.6	12.3	12.5	12.5	12.8	11.3	12.8	12.8	25.4	9.8	10.8	4.2	7.3	90.3	78.8	79.0	79.0	78.6	78.6	78.8	78.2	78.2	77.8	77.8	78.4	79.0	15
16	10.3	1.2	10.3	10.6	11.8	11.8	10.3	11.1	11.8	25.2	8.6	9.8	12.5	12.7	10.5	79.0	79.2	78.6	78.2	78.6	78.4	77.8	77.8	78.0	78.0	78.0	78.6	16
17	25.6	25.6	24.6	24.3	26.2	26.5	26.2	26.5	0.6	24.5	23.1	25.1	25.7	25.7	25.5	99.8	93.3	92.9	93.3	93.1	93.9	93.9	93.9	93.9	95.8	93.3	17	
18	25.3	25.3	24.3	24.0	25.9	26.2	25.3	26.2	26.2	0.8	24.3	22.8	24.8	25.5	25.4	25.2	0.2	93.1	92.7	93.1	92.9	93.7	93.7	93.7	93.7	95.6	93.1	18
19	23.7	26.2	24.0	23.7	23.7	24.8	23.7	24.9	24.8	6.9	24.8	23.7	27.3	25.4	25.4	26.1	7.1	7.3	99.6	99.2	99.8	98.6	98.6	98.2	98.2	96.6	100.0	19
20	24.3	26.8	24.6	24.3	24.3	25.5	24.3	25.5	25.5	7.3	25.4	24.3	27.9	26.0	26.0	26.7	7.6	7.8	0.4	98.8	99.4	98.2	98.2	97.8	97.8	96.2	99.6	20
21	23.7	26.2	24.0	23.7	23.7	24.8	23.7	24.3	24.8	6.9	24.2	23.1	27.9	26.0	26.0	26.1	7.1	7.3	0.8	1.2	99.0	98.2	98.2	97.8	97.8	96.2	99.2	21
22	24.0	26.5	24.3	24.0	24.0	25.2	24.0	25.2	25.2	7.1	25.1	24.0	27.6	25.7	25.7	26.4	7.3	7.6	0.2	0.6	1.0	98.4	98.4	98.0	98.0	96.4	99.8	22
23	24.8	27.4	25.2	24.8	24.8	25.4	24.8	26.1	25.4	6.2	25.4	24.2	28.5	26.6	26.6	27.3	6.4	6.7	1.4	1.8	1.8	1.6	99.6	98.8	98.8	97.2	98.6	23
24	24.8	27.4	25.2	24.8	24.8	26.1	24.8	26.1	26.1	6.2	25.4	24.2	28.5	26.6	26.6	27.3	6.4	6.7	1.4	1.8	1.8	1.6	0.4	98.8	98.8	97.2	98.6	24
25	25.2	27.2	24.9	24.6	25.2	26.1	25.2	25.8	26.1	6.2	25.1	24.2	28.6	26.3	27.3	27.1	6.4	6.6	1.8	2.3	2.3	2.1	1.2	1.2	100.0	96.8	98.2	25
26	25.2	27.2	24.9	24.6	25.2	26.1	25.2	25.8	26.1	6.2	25.1	24.2	28.6	26.3	27.3	27.1	6.4	6.6	1.8	2.3	2.3	2.1	1.2	1.2	0.0	96.8	98.2	26
27	24.6	27.2	24.9	24.6	24.8	25.8	24.6	25.8	25.8	4.2	24.8	23.4	27.6	25.7	26.3	27.1	4.4	4.6	3.5	4.0	4.0	3.8	2.9	2.9	3.3	3.3	96.6	27
28	23.7	26.2	24.0	23.7	23.7	24.8	23.7	24.9	24.8	6.9	24.8	23.7	27.3	25.4	25.4	26.1	7.1	7.3	0.0	0.4	0.8	0.2	1.4	1.4	1.8	1.8	3.5	28

Figure 3. Genetic identity between circulating RHDV and the selected isolate (MW679028 RHDV Maryout).

Results of histopathological examination

Different collected tissues, livers, lungs, kidneys and hearts showed variable histopathological lesions. Livers exhibited diffused coagulative necrosis, hyperplasia in the bile ducts with periductal fibrosis (Figure 4. A, B, C), lungs revealed a picture of peribronchiolar lymphoid proliferation, congestion in the blood capillaries with Oedma, emphysema, and focal haemorrhages in the air alveoli (Figure 5. A, B), kidneys showed diffused coagulative necrosis in the tubular epithelium accompanied with congestion in the glomeruli and Focal haemorrhages in between the tubules (Figure 6. A, B), and hearts also affected with degenerated myocardium, myofibroblasts cells proliferation and Focal inflammatory cells infiltration (Figure 7. A, B). These results were in agreement with Marcato et al 1991 who reported necrosis of the liver followed by disseminated intravascular coagulation with congestion of lungs, trachea and spleen. Cooke et al 2000 observed absence of clinical signs of RHDV in very young rabbits which may initially result from the failure of liver cells or other tissues to support major virus replication but clearly this does not always apply after young wild rabbits come above ground at 3 weeks of age. Mohamed et al 2016 mentioned the natural RHDV outbreak in rabbits showed hemorrhagic rhinitis with submucosal hemorrhages in trachea, bronchi and bronchioles, also lungs exhibited characteristic scattered hemorrhages, liver was congested and friable with reticular pattern of necrosis as well as kidneys and visceral organs revealed Focal hemorrhages.

Figure 4. Livers revealed **A.** periductal fibrosis surrounding the bile ducts at the portal rea associated with coagulative necrosis in the hepatocytes. **B.** hyperplasia in the bile ducts with periductal fibrosis at The portal area. **C.** Diffuse coagulative necrosis all over the hepatocytes in the parenchyma.

Figure 5. lungs showed **A.** peribronchiolar lymphoid proliferation, congestion in the blood vessels and focal haemorrhages in the air alveoli. **B.** Oedma and emphysema in the air alveoli associated with congestion in the blood capillaries.

Figure 6. Kidneys showed **A.** congestion in the glomeruli associated with coagulative necrosis in the tubular epithelium at the cortex. **B.** Focal haemorrhages in between the tubules at the corticomedullary portion.

Figure 7. Hearts exhibited **A, B.** Focal inflammatory cells infiltration with myofibroblasts cells proliferation in between the degenerated myocardium.

Conclusion

It was concluded that the isolate named MW679028 RHDV Maryout gave the same picture of clinical signs, PM lesions and histopathology of classical RHDV as well as it was genetically belonged to RHDV2 and not related to the classic vaccinal strain in Egypt with high nucleotide divergence between them causing high mortalities in both vaccinated and non-vaccinated rabbit flocks. So that a new vaccine of RHDV2 should be applied in rabbit farms with the old classic vaccine at the same time. Finally, continuous studies were recommended on genetic variation and control of RHDV.

Declarations

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they do not have any competing interests.

Authors' contribution

Dr. Selim Salama designed the protocol and applied the molecular analysis, Dr. Hanan El-Samahy planned the work, article writing, and revision, Dr. Disouky Mourad helped in sample collection, laboratory analyses and article writing, Drs. Eman Soliman & Fatma performed molecular biology tests and HA test and Dr. Wael helped in laboratory analyses. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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